

Digital Citizenship in Education: Visioning Safety and Responsibilities in Digital World

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Indeed, people now have to continue to develop and refresh their skills and knowledge in order to keep abreast with the constant innovations and new developments in the digital world (Clement, 2017). Moreover, as technology evolves, our expectation for how that technology can and should make our lives better evolves with it. While holding a paper map may bring out a sense of nostalgia, we know inherently that our phones will help us to navigate to an unknown location more quickly and efficiently. To bring education into the digital age, we must give teachers the skills they need to adapt their classrooms. And teachers can't do it alone - they need district and state leaders to invest in meaningful professional development opportunities that let them explore new teaching practices. That's why digiLEARN, the nonprofit I co-founded that's dedicated to increasing personalized learning options for students and expanding instructional opportunities for educators, has created two resources to empower teachers and schools to transform classrooms through technology. (Perdue, 2017).

This is the fact that technology might give vulnerability on both teachers and students. Suson (2019) stated that there should be a proposed training's and seminars for the teachers relating to digital citizenship and how to be a responsible digital citizen. School management as the starting point of this action plan will be expected to elevate the respondents group or in general to its clientele (the teachers, staff and learners) awareness as to the elements of

ABSTRACT

The inevitability of digital tools and technology usage has accelerated over the past 30 years and continues to grow rapidly. Digital interaction has become a part of everyday life and continues to covers our mind. This research assessed the likelihood of the respondents on how to deal technology properly. Using statistical tool and Survey Questionnaire, the data were analyzed using mean, percentages and t-test two independent samples to measure the significant mean difference of the group respondents. The finding reveals that the group respondents were likely vulnerable when using digital tools. This includes the safety and security and their responsibilities. This study suggests that students and teachers were at risk during this advent of technology.

Keywords: Digital tools, Digital Citizenship, Digital Education, Digital World

1. INTRODUCTION

The digital world is increasingly penetrating the education and skills domain, with technology gradually being used to deliver education, knowledge and skills in new and innovative ways. This penetration is coupled with future changes to the mode and pattern of work, which are themselves affected by the current climate of economic uncertainty, as well as by political shifts. Given the increased use of fast changing digital technologies in the workplace, new skills needs have emerged. The use of these technologies has contributed to transforming learning and skills development into a lifelong process.

digital citizenship through training, seminars, conferences, workshops, posting of tarpaulins and making of school digital citizenship handbook is very essential in providing responsible digital citizen. In addition, the stakeholders involved in the educational system must be fully aware on the norms of responsible behavior with regards to technology use and how to become a responsible digital citizen or known as digital citizenship.

Objective of the Study

This research will transcend the opportunities to understand whether the learners and teachers understand their digital footprint in this digital world.

This is anchored on the framework of the nine elements of digital citizenship of Mike Ribble. The elements give a framework for understanding the technology problems that ar necessary to educators. they ought to be wont to establish current areas of would like during a faculty or district technology program, likewise as rising problems that will become more and more necessary in returning years.

Methodology

This study was used descriptive research method of research. This study utilized the descriptive-normative method of research. Using the adapted Survey Questionnaire, the data were analyzed using mean, percentage and t-test for the significant mean difference.

Results and Discussion

Figure1. Safety and Security

The results shows that educators and learners were in the middle of knowing on how to be safe when dealing with technology in the school and outside premises. According to Reaves (2013) Students have access to more resources and information, allowing them to expand their learning potential beyond their immediate physical environment. However, along with the benefits of mobile devices come the associated challenges. These challenges range from mismanagement and carelessness to misconduct and theft of school devices — often putting students at risk. Ultimately, you must be able to prove good stewardship for the funding you receive. But most importantly, you must establish safeguards for the students that use these devices. Hence, there must be an appropriate strategy employed by the school to avoid problem in terms of integrating technology at school.

Figure2. Responsibilities of digital Users

The data entails, that learners group on was not fully aware on the rights and responsibilities of every users need to follow in the digital age. Looking deeply on the data, teachers were moderately aware but students aren't. Moreover, the data implies that the learners group were not fully aware on how to be effective, thoughtful and becoming a responsible citizen. Thus, it entails that learners group are still novice in

terms of their rights as a digital citizen. Ribble (2015) on his Digital Citizenship within the schools, emphasize Being a full portion in a computerized society infers that each client is overseen beyond any doubt rights, and these rights got to be given essentially to all people. Progressed subjects also have certain obligations to this common open; they ought to assent to live as per the parameters that are commonly settled upon by people. These limits may come as genuine principles or bearings, or as satisfactory utilize techniques. In a perfect world, the people who share within the progressed society would participate to choose a appropriate utilize framework commendable to all.

Moreover, the level of awareness is significantly different. This implies that the awareness of group respondents' as to the nine elements of digital citizenship were not comparable. This is that experience and age gap of the teachers and learners group were a big factor on the results. Moreover, from digital law to digital right and responsibilities, their probability value (Pvalue) are very small compared to the level of significance. Thus, the null hypotheses are rejected. Hence there is significant difference.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Overall, results shows that educators and students were at risk in terms of their safety in this digital world. Moreover, in terms of responsibilities as digital users they were in the middle of knowing what are their rights and responsibilities. This lead to an idea that school are not fully prepare of the trends when integrating technology inside school premises. Educators and students must be aware on their rights and how to be safe in this digital world. Hence, the researcher proposed that there must be an awareness guide that will be conduct in the schools or in the community. This will give the benefits of all the stakeholders. In this way they were able to track their digital footprint in a right way. Moreover, awareness will lead to better life when engage to technology.

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